

PRIORITY DIRECTIONS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. In the article is described the opportunities, advantages and disadvantages of the digital economy development and explores the historical stages of development of this industry in the developed countries of the world. It is analyzed the level of development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan and ways to further develop this sector based on the experience of developed countries, to eliminate existing problems in the sphere.

Keywords: digital economy, information and communication technologies, internet speed, GDP, competitiveness, intensive development, distance learning, online courses, high efficiency, computer literacy.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada raqamli iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning imkoniyatlari, afzalliklari hamda kamchiliklariga ta'rif berilgan bo'lib ushbu sohaning dunyoni rivojlangan mamlakatlari miqyosida tarixiy rivojlanish bosqichlari o'rganilgan. Unda O'zbekistonda raqamli iqtisodiyotning rivojlanganlik darajasi tahlil qilingan hamda rivojlangan mamlakatlar tajribasi asosida bu sohani yanada rivojlantirish, mavjud kamchiliklarni bartaraf etish yo'llari bayon qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: Tayanch iboralar: raqamli iqtisodiyot, axborot-kommunikatsion texnologiyalari, internet tezligi, yalpi ichki mahsulot, raqobatbardoshlik, intensiv rivojlanish, masofaviy ta'lim, onlayn darslar, yuqori samaradorlik, kompyuter savodxonligi.

INTRODUCTION

Digital economy is a system of implementation of economic, social and cultural relations based on the use of digital technologies. It is sometimes referred to as the internet economy, the new economy, or the web economy.

The digital economy is not some other economy that needs to be created from scratch, it means moving the existing economy to a new system by creating new technologies, platforms and business models and introducing them into everyday life. There are several advantages and positive aspects of the digital economy. For example, the development of information and communication technologies can help to save time, which is the most valuable for a person, and to use it effectively. Buying

a printed version of a book is more expensive than buying an electronic version of the same book. It can be seen that we can partly save our money through the development of information and communication technologies. We don't need to wait in line for hours at banks to make utility payments, we will be able to do any work from anywhere. It is also very convenient for women who stay at home or have young children. They can have the opportunity to earn money by doing online sales without leaving their home while doing housework. In addition, it will be possible to effectively use these technologies in the field of education. It is possible to monitor the attendance of pupils and students, to be aware of the results and achievements of learning lessons.

The transition to the digital economy will certainly not affect the increase in production efficiency, the increase in the competitiveness of companies, the reduction of production costs, the creation of new jobs, and the emergence of new modern professions. In short, the development of the digital economy can change our lives in a positive way.⁴

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Digital economy is an electronic business based on digital technologies that allows to significantly increase the efficiency of storage, sale and delivery of various technologies, equipment, goods and services based on the use of process analysis results and processing of large volumes of data. is a set of economic activities closely related to commerce, as well as digital goods and services produced and sold as a result of this activity. It is sometimes referred to as the internet economy, the new economy, or the web economy.

When talking about the process of "digitization" of the economy and society (in English - digitization means digitalization, sometimes digitalization means digitalization), first of all, it is necessary to clarify the terminology. In its broadest sense, the process of "digitization" usually refers to socio-economic change initiated by the widespread adoption and assimilation of digital technologies⁵. The concept of digital economy has been given a number of definitions. In particular, Professor V.

⁴ Parpieva M.M. THE IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN. Scientific electronic journal "Statistics Bulletin of Uzbekistan" of the Institute of Personnel Training and Statistical Research under the State Statistics Committee. 2022, issue 2

⁵ Parpieva M.M. THE IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN. Scientific electronic journal "Statistics Bulletin of Uzbekistan" of the Institute of Personnel Training and Statistical Research under the State Statistics Committee. 2022, issue 2

Ivanov described "Digital economy - a virtual environment that complements our reality" [2]. According to Professor D. Kungurov, there are two approaches to the term "digital economy" - classical and traditional [2]. Digital economy based on digital technologies and describing the exclusive domain of electronic goods and services: the first approach is called "classical", classic examples are telemedicine, distance education, sales of medicines (films, television, books, etc.). The second approach: "digital economy" is economic production using advanced digital technologies. M.L. Kalujskyi defined digital economy as economic Internet activity, as well as its forms, methods, means and communication environment for its implementation [3]. According to the sources, "Digital economy" is a model of this type of economy that works in practice to a certain extent. The digital economy is a production complex, a production system that creates products and services that provide life and comfort for a person, where a certain cyber-physical (cyber-physical) system appears. In our opinion, the digital economy is a virtual environment in which the production complex creates products and services that provide convenience for people, and it is considered an economic production system using digital technologies [3]. Interest in the digital economy has grown significantly due to significant changes in society and the economy. Modern technologies and platforms have helped businesses and individuals to reduce costs by minimizing personal communication with customers, partners, and government organizations, as well as making communication faster and easier.

Nowadays, the concept of digital economy has appeared in the economic theory and practice of a number of countries. It was characterized by the rapid development of digital technologies, the revolution in the information sector, and the acceleration of the globalization of the economy. The efficiency of their use has been translated into increasing knowledge, and socio-economic relations are expanding more and more.

The digital economy is used to represent two different concepts. First, the digital economy is considered a modern stage of development, and it [President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Address of Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis and Senate of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 21, 2020. <http://turkiston.uz> (date of application: 16.03.2020)] is characterized by the priority of creative work and information benefits.⁶

⁶ President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Address of Sh.M. Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis and Senate of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 21, 2020. <http://turkiston.uz> (date of application: 16.03.2020)

Secondly, the digital economy is a unique concept, the object of its study is the information society. In the conditions of today's rapidly developing global economy, the digital economy is in the initial period of its development, and it will take several years before the complete transition to the digital information stage of our time.

As stated by the President of our country, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, "In order to achieve development, it is necessary and necessary for us to acquire digital knowledge and modern information technologies. This gives us the opportunity to take the shortest path to ascension" [1]

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The term "digital economy" was first coined in 1995 by Don Tapcott in *The Digital Economy: Promise and Peril in the Age of Networked Intelligence*. In this publication, fundamental innovations (semiconductors, processors), basic technologies (computers) and connecting infrastructures (internet and telecommunication networks) are distinguished among the main components of the digital economy. The digital economy is used to represent two different concepts. First, the digital economy is considered a modern stage of development, characterized by the priority of creative work and information benefits. Secondly, the digital economy is a unique concept, the object of its study is the information society. In the conditions of today's rapidly developing global economy, the digital economy is in the initial period of its development, and the transition to the digital information stage of our time is only a few decades.

World practice shows that the share of the digital economy in the gross domestic product is one of the indicators of development in this country. Naturally, this indicator is high in developed countries.

The share of the digital economy in the gross domestic product is 10.9% in the USA, 10% in China, 5.5% in India, and less than 2% in Uzbekistan. The development of this field is becoming a requirement of the present time.

The development of the digital economy is an important, strategically important task for Uzbekistan, which determines its competitiveness on a global scale. holds in

There are sufficient opportunities and conditions for the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan, but the development stage is very slow. There are several factors that cause this, the main of which are the low speed and quality of the Internet, the existence of monopolies in many areas, the outdated legislation in the field of information technology, the low level of computer literacy, the lack of

information technology specialists, the lack of information technology security. is not enough.

The term "digital economy" was introduced into scientific practice by Manuel Castells, a Spanish and American sociologist and a leading researcher of the information society. In this regard, he published his three-volume monograph "Information Age: Economy, Society and Culture". To date, the theory of the digital economy has not yet been fully formed and is being widely studied by many economists. In the scientific literature, the modern "New digital economy" is called by different terms. For example, "Post-industrial economy" (D. Bell), "Information economy" (O. Toffler), "Megaeconomy" (V. Kuvaldin), "Economy based on information and communication" (I. Niiniluto), "Techno-economy or digital economy" (B. Gates), "Economy based on knowledge" (D. Tapscott). Mark Porat is one of the American scientists who distinguished between primary and secondary economic sectors.

The primary sector can be clearly evaluated economically because it creates direct market value. Although the secondary sector is considered important for the economy, its economic evaluation is a more difficult task because it includes information activities within companies and state enterprises. Russian scientist N.S. Revenko also studied the changes in the trends of the digital economy in the context of globalization, and V.M. Bondarenko dealt with the issues of formation, development and improvement of the digital economy.

Table 1. Definitions of the digital economy

Description	Definition source
Electronic economy (digital, web, internet economy) - economic activity based on digital technologies related to electronic business and electronic commerce, electronic goods and services produced and sold by them	Wikipedia: https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/E-economy
Network economy (virtual, digital, electronic) - economic activity carried out with the help of electronic networks (digital telecommunications). From a	Glossary.ru: http://www.glossary.ru/cgi-bin/gl_sch2.cgi?RRlylig9!_box

technological point of view, the network economy is a legitimate environment

Digital economy is an economic activity in which information is in digital form. They can increase the productivity of various types of production

Digital economy is computer technology related to digital development. These include: online services, electronic payments, online sales, crossfunding and others.

Digital economy is economic, social and cultural relations based on the use of digital information and communication technologies.

The digital economy is a network of global economic activities used for commercial purposes.

The difference between the digital economy and the ordinary economy.

<http://kremlin.ru/acts/bank/41919>

<http://www.fingramota.org/teoriyafinansov/item/2198-chtotakoetsifrovaya-ekonomika>

<http://www.tadviser.ru/index.php/Article3AdigitalEconomyofRussia>

<http://www.tpinauka.ru/2018/02/Skripko.pdf>

<https://sof.uz/uz/post/raqamli-iqtisodiyot-haqida-nimalarni-bilish-kerak>

The purpose of the research is to shed light on the nature of the digital economy, to identify its advantages and disadvantages, and to develop scientific proposals and practical recommendations for the further development of this field in Uzbekistan.

Research methods. In the process of preparing the article, dialectical, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, scientific abstraction, monographic observation, systematic and comparative analysis methods were used. Main results. When we first hear the term digital economy, what is the "digital economy"? Where did it come from? It is natural that questions arise. If we study the history of the origin of the concept of "digital economy", the digital economy was defined not so long ago, in 1995, by the American scientist Nicholas Negreonte, who works at the University of Massachusetts. He mentioned what changes can be observed in the transition from the old economy to the new economy through the intensive development of information and communication technologies. As mentioned above, until now, the theory of digital economy has not been fully formed and is being widely studied by many economists. "Digital" countries - that is, countries with a

highly developed digital economy today are Norway, Sweden and Switzerland. The USA, Great Britain, Denmark, Finland, Singapore, South Korea and Hong Kong are among the top 10 countries with developed digital economy. Studying the experience of these countries and acting based on them will help to achieve the intended goal faster [4].⁷

In the future perspective of modern development, technologies for working with large-scale data (Big Data), artificial intelligence, neurotechnologies, quantum technologies, Internet of things, robotics and sensors, digital electronic platforms, cloud and mobile technologies, virtual and augmented reality technologies, digital technologies such as crowdsourcing, blockchain technologies, cryptocurrencies and ICOs, 3D-technologies are becoming crucial. It is noted that the digital economy will cause incomparable changes in more than half of the existing industries. For example, according to experts of the World Bank, a 10% increase in the number of high-speed Internet users allows to increase the gross volume of national economies by an average of 0.4-1.4% every year. The rate of growth of the digital economy in the world is almost 20 percent per year. In developed countries, the share of the digital economy in the gross domestic product has reached 7%. They are already benefiting greatly from the introduction of the digital economy. In particular, the United States of America exports more than 400 billion USD of digital services per year. More than 5 percent of the gross domestic product of this country is directly related to the Internet and corresponds to the fields related to information and telecommunication technologies. By 2025, the US will get an additional 20 trillion from the digitization of the industry. dollar income is expected. It is noted that such economic efficiency is especially high in the production of consumer goods (\$10.3 trillion), the automobile industry (\$3.8 trillion), and logistics (\$3.9 trillion). According to the results of various studies, the weight of the digital economy in the world economy ranges from 4.5 to 15.5 percent. Almost 40 percent of the added value created in the global information and communication technology sector and 75 percent of the patents related to blockchain technologies are contributed by the United States of America and the People's Republic of China [4].

In the conditions of globalization of the world economy and technological development, it is difficult to imagine the economic development of Uzbekistan without the digital economy. According to research results, it is estimated that by

⁷ P.Z. Hashimov. Z.F. Fakhridinova. Prospects for the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan. - "ECONOMY OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES" magazine.

2022, a quarter of the global GDP will be in the digital sector. However, the fact that Uzbekistan occupies the 103rd place among more than 170 countries according to the international index of development of information and communication technologies indicates that there are still many issues that need to be solved in this field in our country. will give. The head of our state said that "in 2019, our country has risen by 8 places according to the international index of development of information and communication technologies, but it is still very far behind. It is also true that most ministries, agencies, and enterprises are far from digital technologies. Of course, we know very well that the formation of the digital economy requires the necessary infrastructure, a lot of money and labor resources. Digital technologies not only increase the quality of products and services, but also reduce excess costs. At the same time, they are also an effective tool in eliminating the scourge of corruption, which worries and bothers me a lot. We all need to understand this deeply. It is possible to widely introduce digital technologies in state and community management, and in the social sphere, to increase efficiency, in a word, to dramatically improve people's lives."

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

It should be noted that some elements of the digital economy are already successfully operating in the life of our country. In particular, taking into account the mass transfer of documents and communications to digital means, the authorization of electronic signatures and communication with the state are also being transferred to electronic platforms. According to UN Secretary General António Guterres, "the digital economy can create new risks, including threats to cyber security, facilitation of illegal economic activities, and violations of privacy." Making new decisions requires collaborative action by governments, civil society, academic groups, the scientific community, and the technology sector."

In order to further develop the digital economy, special attention should be paid to the following directions:

1. It is necessary to create sufficient conditions for a complete transition to the digital economy. Including

- creation of new information and communication technologies;
- increasing computer literacy in the country;
- increasing the number of qualified personnel working in this field;
- stimulating the use of digital economy in all branches and sectors of the republic;

- □ increase internet speed and improve its quality;
- □ to ensure that internet services reach remote areas of the country.

2. It is also important to explain to the population why the digital economy is becoming a need of the hour and about its prospects and possibilities, and that it does not consist only of blockchain technologies and cryptocurrencies.

3. In order to support and further develop the competition between electronic commerce (online trade) participants, it is necessary to develop and implement an incentive system.

4. Attracting young personnel to this field, training them in universities of "Digital" countries and helping them improve their skills can make it possible to achieve good results.

Today, in the conditions of Uzbekistan, it is extremely important to study the laws, trends and possibilities of the development of the digital economy on a scientific basis, in particular, the levels of penetration of information technologies into various sectors of the economy. The development and prospects of our country, the success of the reforms being carried out on a large scale in our country directly depend on the introduction of new innovations into our national economy. Therefore, it is important to develop the digital economy, to research its economic, political, social and legal foundations from a scientific and practical point of view.

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